

A Rapid Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Nickel with Di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono using the Synergistic Effect of *o*-Phenanthroline

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Dithizone is widely employed for the separation and colorimetric determination of trace amounts of heavy metals, but it has not been found useful for determining nickel¹. As the spectrum of the nickel chelate is rather complex and does not contain an absorption band of comparable intensity to those of other metals and the rate of formation of the nickel complex is very slow, the attainment of equilibrium may require over an hour of shaking.

In the present work, it was found that the extractability of the nickel-di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono complex into chloroform can be increased by the addition of *o*-phenanthroline and the extracted complex is stable for 2 h which is sufficient to perform analysis. Such synergistic effects are due to an increase in the distribution ratio of a metal chelate on addition of a neutral base such as *o*-phenanthroline. The detailed mechanism of synergistic effects for various metal chelates in the presence of neutral bases has been investigated extensively² and a few applications to analytical chemistry have also been reported³. In general, the mechanism seems to involve the formation of a base adduct of a metal chelate. The synergistic effect in the present extraction results from the formation and the preferential extraction of a phenanthroline adduct of nickel(II)-di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono.

Results and Discussion

During the course of an investigation of adduct and mixed ligand chelate extraction systems, it was found that the addition of heterocyclic nitrogen bases such as pyridine and phenanthroline to a chloroform solution of di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono helps extractibility of

the metal more than di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono used alone. Nickel was rapidly and quantitatively extracted over a broad pH range (5.5–11.0) to give a highly coloured mixed ligand complex having an absorption band centred at 500 nm. The mixed ligand complex is sufficiently stable to permit the removal of excess of di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono by back-extraction with 0.1M sodium hydroxide, so a 'monocolour' method is applicable. The molar absorptivity of this complex was found to be $66.33 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which makes the method about four times as sensitive as the dimethylglyoxime method using an oxidising agent⁴.

Experimental

Visible absorption spectra were measured with a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 2000 spectrophotometer. All the reagents used were of analytical grade.

Di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono was prepared by the reported method⁵ involving persulphate oxidation of di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono and then purified⁶. Di-*o*-tolylthiocarbazono was synthesised by the reported method⁷.

General procedure : To an aliquot (1–10 μg Ni/10 ml) was added acetate buffer (5 ml; pH 6.0) followed by chloroform solution (15 ml, diTT $7 \times 10^{-5}M$, phen $3 \times 10^{-5}M$) and the mixture was shaken for 5 min when the two phases were separated. The chloroform layer was back-extracted with sodium hydroxide (10 ml; 0.1M) shaking vigorously for about 1 min. The absorbance of the chloroform layer was determined at 500 nm against a reagent blank. A calibration curve was constructed and then the concentration of Ni determined.

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